

Aerodynamic and aeroacoustic design optimization of UAVs using a surrogate model

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ABSTRACT

A multi-disciplinary design optimization framework is proposed to improve the noise emissions of a quadcopter in forward flight with only a small penalty in aerodynamic performance. The design parameters are the spanwise distribution of the sweep angle and chord length of the propeller blades. The intention is to minimize the aerodynamic interactions between the propellers, as well as with the airframe, as they are associated with the tonal noise emissions that are known to dominate the radiated acoustic field in such applications. The noise prediction is obtained following the principles of the aeroacoustic analogy, using in this work a URANS CFD solver for the calculation of the unsteady blade loading, and an in-house aeroacoustic solver for the resulting acoustic radiation. The results demonstrate that the aerodynamic and acoustic performance cannot be improved simultaneously if the noise level is estimated using an unweighted sound metric, but that significant noise reduction can be achieved with a minor degradation of the mean thrust when the A-weighted noise emissions are taken as objective function.

1. Introduction

Unmanned air vehicles (UAVs), also commonly called drones, are expected to be widely used in various fields in the near future. Targeted applications of these vehicles include medical emergency services, parcel delivery, or the inspection of remote industrial installations such as off-shore wind turbines. However, UAVs generate noise pollution in the nearby communities, which is a concern for their widespread operation and acceptance. For public acceptance, noise pollution is going to be a significant problem [1]. The noise is generated by the propellers driven by electric motors, emitting tonal noise at discrete multiples of the Blade Passing Frequency (BPF) [2] as well as broadband noise at higher frequencies.

The present work is focused on the tonal noise component, acknowledged as the main cause of acoustic annoyance of drones [1], being even more annoying than turbofan aircraft [3] or helicopters [4]. This annoyance has been quantified through psycho-acoustic

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indicators based on sound quality metrics such as loudness, sharpness, fluctuation strength, etc. [5]. A recent study confirmed that among those metrics, loudness plays a dominant role in the subjective assessment of drone annoyance [4]. In their work, the annoyance is also quantified by psycho-acoustic metrics.

Since tonal noise is associated with periodic forces exerted by the blades and airframe components, a sensible objective for an aeroacoustic optimization is the mitigation of the aerodynamic interactions of the propeller blades with the vorticity and non-homogeneity shed by adjacent propellers [6] or with the airframe [7,8]. The interactions of propellers are shown for a quadcopter in [9] in forward flight at 10 m/s. They have shown that significant reductions of thrust occur at the rear propellers compared to the isolated rotor case.

In rotating machines, the blade region close to the tip is often the main contributor to the noise emissions, due to the fastest rate of change of the blade loading combined with the largest Doppler amplification. The blade tip vortex noise can as well be an important source, where the tip vortex circulation results from the spanwise distribution of the blade sectional lift. Therefore, changing blade properties such as sweep angle and spanwise chord modulation plays an important role in blade loading, and subsequently on the generated noise. This is supported by previous studies having demonstrated that up to 5 dB of noise reduction is possible with the addition of blade sweep [10]. Similarly, tonal noise could be reduced by 5 dB as well for helicopters in forward flight with the help of a swept tip [11]. A swept tip can provide major noise reductions over straight and tapered tips. In an optimization study [12], tip sweep was implemented on an unswept blade for a helicopter in hover conditions. Airbus Helicopters BlueEdge rotors reduce the BVI noise as much as 4 dB(A) in descent conditions [13].

Obviously, constraints related to the admissible mechanical stresses would have to be taken into account in a realistic propeller optimization exercise. This important aspect lies however beyond the scope of the present work, as it would otherwise require assumptions on the manufacturing technologies and materials, and eventually limit our aerodynamic and acoustic design space. The outcomes of the present work may nevertheless guide the selection of the materials, by indicating which blade shapes would be desirable from the aero-acoustic standpoint, and therefore which mechanical properties may be needed in terms of resistance, deformation under aerodynamic loads and centrifugal forces, etc.

In light of the above, the present study proposes using A-weighting to reflect the effects of drone noise on humans. The shape optimization of the blade tip region is carried out, with the deformation being achieved by sweeping the blade in its rotation plane, combined with a spanwise modulation of the blade chord.

With the above notions in mind, the numerical aero-acoustic optimization of a multicopter requires the prediction of the unsteady flow induced by and traversed by the propeller blades. Low-fidelity (panel codes, vortex lattice methods), medium-fidelity (Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes, URANS), and high-fidelity (e.g. Large Eddy Simulation, LES) tools can be used to this end, satisfying different needs with different resource demands. Examples can be found in the literature about the application of full potential solvers [14], nonlinear vortex lattice method [15], 2-D panel solvers [16], Lattice-Boltzmann Method [17] or Detached Eddy Simulation [18]. The lower-order methods have faster turnaround times and would be useful in preliminary design phases. However, these solvers often fail to capture effects like blade-vortex interactions or unsteady blade stall. Therefore they yield only a crude estimation of the flow field. High-fidelity solvers yield more accurate results, at the expense of larger computational runtimes. They are typically involved in the final design stages or provide cross-validation and fine-tuning data to the lower-order methods.

According to the present authors' experience, quadcopter tonal noise can be predicted by solving URANS equations with a fair accuracy [7], at least for the first BPF harmonics that usually dominate the noise spectrum. The question that is addressed with this work is whether URANS, combined with an aeroacoustic analogy, can provide an acceptable accuracy/runtime trade-off for the aeroacoustic optimization of multicopter drones. In addition, while most of the optimization studies in the literature have tackled hovering conditions [12,16,19,20], this work is considering an operation causing more complex rotor–rotor interactions: forward horizontal flight.

The paper is organized as follows: the aeroacoustic prediction approach and the optimization chain are described in Section 2, together with the geometry and case set-up for the URANS solution; the effects of the tip-on-tip and tip-on-strut interactions observed on the baseline and optimized quadcopters are analyzed and discussed in Section 3 and conclusions are given in Section 4.

2. Numerical optimization strategy

The optimization chain is visualized in Fig. 1. The VKI in-house optimization tool CADO [21] is used to generate the necessary design of experiments to train a surrogate model, and subsequently optimize the propellers.

The optimization loop involves mesh deformation, aerodynamic computation by means of URANS, free-field acoustic calculation, and objective and constraint calculation. The different steps are detailed below, starting with the presentation of the baseline configuration.

2.1. Baseline configuration

The baseline geometry used in this work is the DJI Phantom III drone, based on the same airframe as the previous Phantom II, both having been thoroughly investigated experimentally [22] and numerically [23]. The pre-existing data has already permitted validating the aeroacoustic simulation chain used in this work for the Phantom III drone in hovering conditions [7].

The drone is assumed to be in forward horizontal translation, at a speed of 10 m s^{-1} and with a pitch angle of -5 deg . These conditions are realistic conditions that DJI Phantom III drone can face during its operation [24].

Fig. 1. Optimization chain.

The rotational speed of all propellers is fixed at 6000 RPM. While being realistic, this unique value ignores the fact that the RPM of the front and back propellers may have to be different in order to counter a pitching moment of the vehicle during forward translation. This data is unfortunately unknown for this commercial drone. Besides, preserving the same RPM in forward flight as in the former study by Zarri et al. [7] for hovering conditions permits a better understanding of the noise-generating mechanisms associated with the alteration of the flow topology. Adding to the picture the variation of rotor RPM, which is certainly a necessary step in the future, would now blur the results and hinder their interpretation.

Another needed arbitrary parameter is the clocking angle of the propellers. In this work, we have assumed that the propellers are clocked in such a way that the blade tips of adjacent propellers find their minimum possible separation (i.e. are facing each other) once per revolution, thereby maximizing their mutual influence at this clocking position. This choice, initially made by [7] to compare the tip-tip and blade-strut interactions, will permit here to highlight the potential for attenuating the tip-to-tip interaction noise mechanism by means of blade sweep. Conversely, a legitimate question is whether the result of the optimization that will be shown below would persist for a more general relative clocking situation, where strong tip-tip interactions would be less favored. We will come back to this point when analyzing the results.

2.2. Unsteady RANS simulations

The Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) equations are solved using a commercial CFD code, STAR-CCM+ [25]. Due to the low Mach number, the energy equation is not solved, and the density is allowed to vary according to the ideal gas law as a function of pressure (the flow being considered isothermal). The p - V coupling is done via the SIMPLE method. The spatial discretization scheme provides second-order accuracy on both convective and turbulence quantities. The turbulence is modeled by SST k - ω model [26] with all y^+ wall treatment. The outer boundaries are placed at a distance exceeding 50 propeller diameters $D = 0.239$ m. A velocity inlet and pressure outlet boundary conditions are used.

The unsteady solutions are initialized with a moving reference frame (MRF) steady-flow solution [7]. The sliding mesh technique is used to rotate the propellers. One timestep corresponds to 3 deg of propeller rotation. At a rotational frequency of 100 Hz, the corresponding Δt is 83.333 μ s.

The rotation direction and the naming convention for the propellers are given in Fig. 2. The front blades are CCW2 and CW1, and the aft blades are CW2 and CCW1. CW indicates a clockwise rotation, whereas CCW means counter-clockwise rotation. While the front propellers are ingesting relatively clean inflow, the aft ones are traversing a significantly more disturbed flow induced by the front propellers. The unsteady solution is carried out for 1200 timesteps, corresponding to 10 revolutions of the propellers. At each time step, a minimum of 30 sub-iterations are calculated. The maximum number of sub-iterations is also capped at 50 in the

Fig. 2. Propeller naming convention and rotation directions.

Fig. 3. Sliding mesh topology.

Fig. 4. Vertical mesh slice containing the axis of two diagonally opposite propellers.

case of inner convergence criteria not being reached. It was verified that this condition never occurred past transient effects related to the initial starting condition.

The mesh resolution is similar to that used by Zarri et al. [7]. There are approximately 200,000 polyhedral faces on a propeller. The prism layers are generated near walls, achieving a near-wall resolution with y^+ in the range 1–2 at the surface of the blades. In total, around 12.5 million polyhedral cells (with 57 million vertices) are generated. The airframe is modeled with a no-slip surface. The sliding mesh interface between fluid regions is shown in Fig. 3, whereas Fig. 4 shows a vertical slice cutting through the mesh, illustrating the successive refinement boxes.

2.3. Aeroacoustic simulation

The formalism offered by the Ffowcs Williams–Hawkins (FWH) analogy [27] has been followed to predict the drone tonal noise emissions. Given the low tip Mach number ($M_{\text{tip}} = 0.22$) and the acoustic compactness of the blades for the first BPF harmonics, the contributions of the quadrupolar and thickness noise have been omitted [28]. Those equivalent sources are indeed of secondary

Fig. 5. Propeller strips defined for the acoustic calculations.

importance compared with the loading noise at low tip Mach numbers. Besides, they are hardly amenable to optimization. The thickness of the blades of drone propellers is often the minimum that can be achieved while ensuring structural integrity, and the Reynolds stresses linked with the quadrupoles are associated with aerodynamic mechanisms that are too intricate to be optimized through shape control.

The tonal noise is thus mainly associated with the steady and periodic components of the blade forces, considered as equivalent rotating dipoles [2,28]. The acoustic pressure in the geometric far-field of each strip is given by:

$$p_{nB} \simeq -\frac{iBk_{nB}}{4\pi} \frac{e^{-ik_{nB}x}}{x} \sum_{p=-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-i(nB-p)(\varphi-\pi/2)} J_{-nB+p}(-k_{nB}R_0 \sin \theta) \left[F_p^{(T)} \cos \theta - \frac{nB-p}{k_{nB}R_0} F_p^{(D)} \right], \quad (1)$$

for the n th harmonic of the BPF, B is the number of blades, $k_{nB} = nB\Omega/c_0$ with Ω the propeller angular frequency, x is the listener distance and R_0 is the radius where the force is applied. φ and θ are the listener's azimuthal and polar angles, respectively. $F_p^{(T)}$ and $F_p^{(D)}$ are the p th harmonics of the thrust and drag, respectively, exerted by each blade of our propellers on the fluid. These Blade Loading Harmonics (BLHs) are calculated in a reference frame attached to the blade.

Eq. (1) provides a simple explanation of the contribution of each BLH p to the noise perceived at the n th harmonic of the BPF. J is the Bessel function of the first kind, parameterized by the integer order $-nB+p$, acting as a weighting factor for each BLH harmonic p of the summation. The argument of $J_{-nB+p}(-k_{nB}R_0 \sin \theta)$ involves the product of the rotating dipole tangential Mach number ($k_{nB}R_0 = nBM_{tg}$) by the sine of the listener polar angle. This argument is thus assumed to take small values for low subsonic tip Mach numbers. In our instance, the blade tip Mach number is equal to 0.22. Considering the functional shape of our Bessel function for small arguments, it follows that the tonal noise received at the angular frequency $nB\Omega$ is predominantly generated by the BLH of order $p = nB\Omega$, with smaller contributions from the adjacent BLHs.

In the numerical implementation of this equation, the BLHs are integrated over small segments dividing the blade surface in the spanwise and chordwise directions. Those segments, also called strips, must be (i) acoustically compact and (ii) small enough to resolve the spanwise and chordwise variations of the amplitude and phase of the equivalent dipoles borne by each strip. Following a convergence study, each blade has been divided into 30 sections in the spanwise direction, and into 2 sections in the chordwise direction (Fig. 5).

The above theory has been implemented in an in-house Python-based solver, named BATMAN^x (Broadband And Tonal Models for Airfoil Noise). Based on the acoustic pressure, BATMAN^x integrates the acoustic intensity over a downward-oriented hemispherical surface to yield a sound power level

$$L_{W,n} = 10 \log_{10} \frac{\int_{S_{\text{hemi}}} |p_{nB}|^2 / (\rho_0 c_0) dS}{10^{-12} \text{ W}} \quad [\text{dB}],$$

used as objective function to minimize the optimization.

It must be noted that for this optimization exercise, the scattering of the propeller noise by the drone airframe has been neglected, despite the fact that near-field scattering effects were previously shown to induce a substantial re-distribution of the drone directivity map [7]. Nevertheless, it can be argued that by integrating the sound intensity over a surface, those directivity alterations would be averaged out, yielding similar values of the objective function with or without scattering effects. But this point deserves to be confirmed through further investigations.

The sound power level has been calculated for the first 5 BPF harmonics, of which the first had consistently the largest amplitude. For this reason, the acoustic optimization has been carried out targeting the first harmonic of the BPF in a first step. However, as the results below will demonstrate, this choice of objective function, combined with a constraint on the mean thrust, did not permit achieving significant gains.

For this reason, in a second step, the sound power spectrum has been considered after A-weighting [29] the sound pressure amplitudes, giving the A-weighted sound power level harmonics $L_{W(A),n}$, expressed in dB(A). With this filtering, reflecting better the human perception, the dominant tone appeared to be the third harmonic of the BPF (Fig. 6), which was then selected as the acoustic objective function.

2.4. Blade mesh morphing

The alteration of the blade geometry has been directly performed at the mesh level, using a Free Form Deformation (FFD) morphing technique implemented in the open-source Python toolbox PyGeM [30]. A set of control points, which form the lattice

Fig. 6. SWL for the first 5 BPF harmonics, unweighted vs. A-weighted.

Fig. 7. FFD lattice enclosing the propeller.

for the FFD box, are defined by

$$\mathbf{P}_{i,j,k}^0 = [i/l, j/m, k/n]^T. \tag{2}$$

The number of control points depends on the desired order of Bernstein polynomials, i.e. l, m, n . Indices i, j, k correspond to x, y, z directions, respectively. Therefore, the parameter vector, which will control the deformations of the object enclosed in the lattice is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_{i,j,k} = 3 \times (l + 1) \times (m + 1) \times (n + 1). \tag{3}$$

It is possible to compute a mapping ψ that maps physical axes to non-dimensional u, v and w axes:

$$\psi : (x, y, z) \mapsto (u, v, w) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \times [0, 1]. \tag{4}$$

The control points \mathbf{P} (Eq. (2)) are updated using the deformation (Eq. (3)):

$$\mathbf{P}_{i,j,k} = \mathbf{P}_{i,j,k}^0 + \boldsymbol{\mu}_{i,j,k},$$

and the deformed control points are obtained from the inverse mapping [31]:

$$\psi^{-1} : (u, v, w) \mapsto (x, y, z). \tag{5}$$

With the help of inverse mapping, it is then possible to compute X ,

$$X(u, v, w) = \sum_{i=0}^l \sum_{j=0}^m \sum_{k=0}^n \mathbf{P}_{i,j,k} B_i^l(u) B_j^m(v) B_k^n(w),$$

where B_i^l is the Bernstein polynomial of degree l ,

$$B_i^l(u) = \binom{l}{i} (1-u)^{l-i} u^i.$$

In this study, the FFD control points are fixed in z (aligned with the rotor axis), in order to fix the thickness distribution of the blade at every airfoil section. The control points can thus only move in the plane perpendicular to the rotor axis. In Fig. 7, the FFD box generated around one blade is shown, which has dimensions of $2 \times 9 \times 2$.

Fig. 8. Effects of chord design variable (a), and the sweep design variable (b) on the propeller geometry.

Fig. 9. Blade deformation achieved by the FFD morphing technique, comparing invalid deformation (a) and extreme deformation (b).

For the control of the blade deformation, using the positions of the FFD control points as parameters would lead to a prohibitive number of degrees of freedom. Instead, the displacements of the FFD control points are linked through two parameters only, relating to the sweep and chord length (Fig. 8), balancing computational cost and optimization potential.

The sweep parameter rotates all the FFD points about the $+z$ -axis, except the $j = 0$. The $j = 0$ plane is the inboard part of the blade, which is held fixed for continuity purposes. The chord parameter controls the chord length at midspan. The first and last two FFD points are not modified, meaning that their chord lengths are kept the same. The other points are moved in a symmetric manner that either causes an increase or decrease in the chord length depending on the sign of the design variable. The effects of the chord parameter are shown in Fig. 8(a). The left blade shape is obtained with a value of -0.3 and the right one is obtained with a value of 0.3 . The values are normalized with respect to the FFD box length in the respective deformation axis. The effects of the blade sweep are shown in Fig. 8(b). The counterclockwise swept propeller is obtained with a value of 24 deg, and the clockwise swept one is obtained with a value of -24 deg. The rotation approach guarantees that the swept blade does not touch the sliding mesh boundaries, which is discussed next.

It is noted that due to sliding mesh boundary constraint, it is not possible to freely move the control points in the x - y plane. If the control points are used to impose a sweep on the blade without any constraints, then the propeller is likely to cross the sliding mesh boundary. For example, if the control points are moved *only* in x direction, invalid blade shapes may be obtained. If the deformation is large, the blade shape is going to be invalid. The crossing of the sliding mesh boundary means the CFD simulation will fail because the meshing is problematic due to rotational volumes not being watertight anymore.

In Fig. 9(a), the valid and invalid deformations are shown. If the control points are moved in only the x direction, the purple blade is obtained. Even though it is a manifold shape (i.e. shape itself is watertight), it is invalid since it crosses the sliding mesh boundary. Therefore, with the help of rotation of the control points, the blade shape does not intersect with the sliding mesh boundary as shown in Fig. 9(b). With this approach, it is guaranteed that the sliding mesh boundary will not be crossed, resulting in a robust parametrization and mesh deformation technique.

Exp. ID	Sweep	Chord
0	0	0
1	24	0.3
2	24	-0.3
3	-24	0.3
4	-24	-0.3

Fig. 10. Change in the objective function vs. iterations, when the penalty is defined as $L_{W,1}$.

2.5. Optimizer

The optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{p}} L_{W,n}(\mathbf{p}) \quad \text{under the constraint} \quad \bar{L} \geq 0.9 \bar{L}_0, \quad (6)$$

with the parameters vector \mathbf{p} exploring the parameter space

$$\begin{bmatrix} -40 \\ -0.5 \end{bmatrix} \leq \begin{bmatrix} p_1 \\ p_2 \end{bmatrix} \leq \begin{bmatrix} 40 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $L_{W,n}$ is the integrated sound power level at the BPF n , \bar{L} is the time-averaged lift of the drone, $\bar{L}_0 = 19.75$ N is the baseline time-averaged lift, and p_1 and p_2 are the sweep and chord parameters, respectively. As evoked in Section 2.3, the optimization has been carried out using an objective function $L_{W,1}$ in the first step, and $L_{W,3}$ after.

Given the significant airframe area that is swept by the propellers' slipstreams, it has been felt necessary to include in the lift calculation the contribution of the surface-integrated pressure field over the airframe. The total lift used as a constraint is therefore the sum of the 4 propeller thrusts (projected in the vertical direction) and of the airframe lift. In practice, it appeared that the lift induced by the airframe is only a small correction, of the order of 5%–10%, of the total thrust provided by the propellers.

A Differential Evolution (DE) method is used to carry out this optimization, which does not require gradient information. The differential evolution algorithm works on the design space estimated by a surrogate model obtained through Kriging. This model offers the best linear unbiased estimator and does not require an estimation of the order of the objective function, making it superior to the polynomial response surface model [32,33].

The Kriging model is trained with the help of a Design of Experiments (DoE). Each design variable is perturbed to 20% and 80% values of the maximum range, where the initial value of the design variable (i.e. zero) is considered to be at 50%. The initial design of experiments is given in Table 1.

A typical optimization history is shown in Fig. 10 below (in this instance with $L_{W,1}$ as objective function). The optimization had been started with a constraint of lift being at least equal to the baseline. The result was the first 5 points of the optimization history, with no achievable noise reduction. However, relaxing the lift constraint to 90% of the baseline as in Eq. (6) has permitted starting exploring the parameter space. The green dots indicate propeller geometries that satisfy the lift constraint, while the geometries identified by the blue dots do not satisfy the constraint. The red line shows the evolution of the best design.

The necessity to relax the thrust constraint is best illustrated in Fig. 11, showing the design space explored by the optimizer. The design space permitted by the initial $\bar{L} \geq \bar{L}_0$ constraint reduces to an extremely narrow region around the baseline parameter

Fig. 11. Design space explored by the optimizer.

vector $(p_1, p_2) = (0, 0)$. In contrast, the design space limited by the $\bar{L} \geq 0.9 \bar{L}_0$ constraint opens up to the boundary indicated by the red line in Fig. 11. The behavior of the objective function does not seem to exhibit concaveness, therefore it may be expected to find optima near the constraint boundary.

3. Results

In the following subsections, we will start by analyzing the flow topology and blade forces of the baseline configuration, in order to identify the dominant interactions that are associated with the blade force unsteadiness and eventually BLH spectrum. The results of the optimization are presented after.

3.1. Baseline: aerodynamic interactions and blade loading harmonics

We analyze here the time evolution of the blade forces, in a view to identify the interactions causing those fluctuations. Fig. 12 shows the topology of the vortical structures, highlighted using the iso-surfaces of Q-criterion, at successive time steps spanning over half a revolution of the propellers: $t/T_{\text{rot}} = [0, 1/12, \dots, 6/12]$. With each flow visualization, the total thrust experienced by each blade during the half-revolution is plotted with a vertical line marking the corresponding phase. Fig. 12a designates the blades that are followed during the time sequence. The blade-turbulence interactions during the second half ($t/T_{\text{rot}} = [7/12, 8/12, \dots, 12/12]$) can be inferred by looking at the opposite blade.

An analysis was conducted in Ref. [7] for the same drone in hover, indicating that the dominant interactions were the propeller blades' tip-to-tip and blade-to-strut interactions. The periodic blade forces were fairly similar for the blades of the 4 propellers, which could be explained by the two perpendicular symmetry planes that can be drawn when looking at the propeller-propeller and propeller-strut interactions.

As evidenced in the flow visualizations, forward translation brings an additional level of complexity, with the front rotors CW1 and CCW2 shedding vortical structures that are seen to interact with the aft rotors CCW1 and CW2. In contrast with the hovering case, the history of the blade forces is now quite different for the front and aft rotor blades. For a rotational period, the frontal blades generally generate more loading, as they receive slightly less disturbed flow from the freestream. This corresponds to the orientation in which the advancing side blade interacts with the tip vortex shed by the upstream propeller (Figs. 12c, 12d, the other unmarked blade). After passing through the tip vortex, the generated thrust (lift) decreases. It is noted that the variance of the overall thrust is higher in the aft blades, as expected due to the presence of upstream blades.

Looking at the variation of thrust with respect to blade positions, Figs. 12a and 12b indicate that the initial tip-on-tip interaction between fore and aft propellers are weak interactions for selected blades. However, directly after this tip-on-tip interaction, blades on the fore propellers reach a value that is comparable to their maximum thrust due to strong tip-on-strut interactions (Fig. 12c) [7]. Similarly, a slight reduction in the thrust of the aft propeller blades is observed, which is on the order of 10%. The strongest and fastest increase of blade thrust is observed when the blade is passing over its supporting strut, at $t/T_{\text{rot}} = 3/12$ (Fig. 12c), similarly

Fig. 12. Time evolution of vortical structures and total thrust produced on a reference blade of each propeller, Q-criterion level 150,000 [$1/s^2$]. The drone is flying towards the reader.

as in hover. A striking difference with the hover case is that at nearly the same moment, the blades of the *aft* rotors passing over their own struts experience a *negative* fluctuation of thrust. It appears that in forward flight, the temporal variation of the blade angle of attack is reversed for the front and aft propellers when the blade is passing in the vicinity of the supporting strut. (It can indeed be reasonably assumed that the blade force fluctuations are essentially related to the variation of the angle of attack of the outer part of the blade, the flight speed being negligible compared with the blade tip Mach number [9].)

Then, in the final tip-on-tip interaction between two fore blades (Figs. 12d, 12e) the thrust of the frontal propeller blades increases slightly, even though the propellers ingest their own tip vortices shed from the other blade. The tip-on-tip interaction between the aft propellers increases also slightly the generated thrust for both blades, which can be considered as a weak interaction. A gradual increase of the aft rotor blade thrust is observed, peaking when it moves against the mean flow and interacts with the tip vortex shed by the front rotor, around $t/T_{rot} = 11/12$ (Fig. 12e). In Fig. 12f, the frontal blades start to lose their thrust (transition into retreating side), and the aft blades start to increase their thrust (transition into advancing side).

Taking the Fourier transform of the time signals shown in Fig. 12 yields the BLH spectra, shown in Fig. 13. The spectra are shown separately for the front and aft blades, and compared with the spectra that were obtained by Zarri et al. [7] in hovering conditions (but for the same geometry, RPM and relative clocking angles between the propellers).

It appears that the mean thrust (harmonic of order 0) is not much affected by the effect of forward flight. In contrast, the higher BLHs until order 10 or so are more significantly impacted, with a nearly tenfold amplification of the BLHs of order 1, reaching nearly equal levels for both front and aft rotor blades. For the second BLH, the aft blades see a much stronger amplification than

Fig. 12. (continued).

Fig. 13. Blade thrust loading harmonics for hover and forward flight conditions.

Fig. 14. Baseline and optimized SWL spectra (a, b) and blade planforms (c, d) with counterclockwise rotation direction.

the front ones. The aft blades see also an increase in their BLHs of orders 3 and 4, while for the same orders, the front blades' BLHs are actually attenuated with respect to the hovering conditions.

The spectrum of the aft rotor blades is more amplified for the low orders (3-5), while the spectrum of the front rotor blades is more amplified for orders 7-20. This may be related to the time diagrams of Fig. 12, which shows that the surge of thrust associated with the blade-to-strut interactions occur over shorter time scales for the front rotors than for the aft rotors.

Beyond order 25, the aft propeller blade BLHs are seen to level out, in contrast with the front propeller BLHs, which decrease at the same constant rate as in hovering conditions. This might be related to the turbulent fluctuations ingested by the aft rotor, seemingly associated with broadband load fluctuations, but we should take care of not over-interpreting these results, bearing in mind the limited capacity of URANS to simulate a broad range of turbulent scales.

3.2. Aeroacoustic optimization

The results of the aeroacoustic optimization can be compared in Fig. 14 for the cases where the objective function is either $L_{W,1}$ or $L_{W(A),3}$, together with the corresponding optimized planforms.

In the first case, the optimizer yields a blade that has been forward swept (≈ 21 deg) with increased chord length in the midspan. This design satisfies the constraint, with a total time-averaged lift equal to 91.6% of the baseline lift. The sound power level is decreased by about 1 dB at the first harmonic of the BPF, with similar reductions at the second and third harmonics of the BPF. The fourth harmonic of the BPF sees its level increased, while the fifth harmonic is not affected.

The acoustic benefits are much more significant when the spectrum is A-weighted and the third (now loudest) BPF is selected as objective function. The optimized blade is still forward-swept, but up to approximately 40 deg, and again with a slight chord increase. The sound power level reduction at the third harmonic of the BPF reaches about 3.5 dB, and remains appreciable at the other BPFs as well. Furthermore, the total lift drops to 92.1% of its baseline value, i.e. a little better than in the previous case.

It appears thus that only a small noise reduction can be obtained when selecting $L_{W,1}$ as objective function, which contrasts with the significant abatement obtained when trying to minimize $L_{W(A),3}$. This is explained considering Eq. (1) in combination with the BLH spectrum shown in Fig. 13. We have seen that the BLH that contributes the most to the first harmonic of the BPF is $p = 2$, since the Bessel function decays relatively fast for integer orders different from zero, i.e. for $nB \neq p$ in Eq. (1). However, the fact that the steady loading is one order of magnitude larger than the BLH $p = 2$ still makes it the dominant contributor to the summation, even after being weighted down by the small value of the Bessel function J_2 . As a result, the optimizer is unable to reduce $L_{W,1}$ without degrading the mean lift \bar{L} , the latter being strongly constrained in this optimization exercise. This is related to the fact that the initial blade is already a 'good' aerodynamic design, near an optimum point for $L_{W,1}$.

Fig. 15. Evolution of the total lift and sound power level for the two different choices for the objective function. The dashed horizontal line marks the 90% minimum constraint on the total lift.

This is also evidenced by the optimization convergence history (Fig. 15), which shows the evolution of the total lift and integrated sound power level along the optimizer iterations. The correlation between the lift and $L_{W,1}$ is manifest, as well as the difficulty of the optimizer to converge to stable values of both variables. In contrast, the lift appears to be much less correlated with $L_{W(A),3}$, giving thereby much more freedom to the optimizer, which converges to a stable solution after only 15 iterations.

The blade loading harmonics of the fore and aft propellers (Fig. 16) provide a finer analysis of the optimization results. It appears that the forces experienced by the front blades remain relatively unchanged by the optimization, whichever objective function, $L_{W,1}$ or $L_{W(A),3}$, is used. In contrast, the aft propeller blades see a much more significant decrease in their amplitudes, for harmonics beyond the order $p = 10$. To explain this attenuation of the highest harmonics, we conjecture that the optimized blade having a substantial sweep angle, the interaction of the aft blades with the tip vortex shed by the front rotor is phase-shifted along the aft blades span. One can qualitatively expect that ‘smoothing’ such interactions over time may have the effect of a low-pass filter on the integrated blade loading harmonics.

In any case, those high BLH orders are not expected to contribute much to the summation in (1) for the BPFHs $n = 1$ and 3 taken as objective functions. The BLHs that should contribute the most to the $L_{W(A),3}$ value (i.e. the BLHs close to the order $p = 6$) seem a little bit more dampened than those contributing to $L_{W,1}$ ($p = 2$), which would at least partly explain the more significant noise reduction after optimization. But we conjecture also that the noise reduction was not only achieved by the diminution of the BLHs amplitudes but also through phase effects. While the potential interaction of the blade with the supporting struts will take place with the same phase for all blade segments, there will be a spreading of the interaction phases for a swept blade. This would mitigate the constructive interferences of the acoustic emissions of different blade segments.

In Fig. 17, the thrust distribution of a revolution is presented for each of the propellers for the baseline configuration. For the two front propellers, the thrust fluctuations are seemingly associated with their tip–tip interaction and tip–strut interactions. The tip–tip interactions between the front and back propellers appear to be much weaker, causing fairly negligible changes in thrust. The aft propeller blades also produce high thrust when they move against the mean flow. The thrust distribution for the optimized configurations, minimizing either the first or third harmonics of the blade passing frequency, are shown in Fig. 18. The tip–tip interaction between the frontal propellers is reduced for both cases, but is more important when the optimization is carried out for $L_{W(A),3}$.

The difference between optimized cases and the baseline case (delta) is shown in Fig. 19. When $L_{W(A),1}$ is minimized (Fig. 19(a)), the tips of the frontal blades are producing slightly more thrust in the flight direction, compared with the baseline, with less loading at the midsection of these blades. A net thrust loss is nevertheless observed, for both optimization cases. Optimizing the blades for $L_{W,3}$ causes only a minor attenuation of the loads in the region where nearby tip–tip interactions are expected. The reduction is at its peak near blade midspan, and is mostly visible along a forward arc. In both optimization cases, the effect of blade sweep is significant, and similar, for the aft propellers. It appears that the peak of lift that is generated when the rear propeller blades interact with the tip vortex shed by the frontal propellers is substantially attenuated.

These observations provide a tentative answer to the question that was raised at the end of Section 2.1, i.e. whether the benefits of the present shape optimization would persist in a more general clocking configuration, with weaker tip–tip interactions. The fact that the strongest reduction of the loads shown in Fig. 19 is not found at the tip–tip interaction region, but (i) for the rear propeller, where it interacts with the front rotor tip vortex, and (ii) over a forward arc of the front propellers, suggests that noise reduction would also be obtained in a more general clocking configuration. However this should be verified carefully through further simulations.

Given the loss of net thrust, a fair comparison between the baseline and acoustically optimized rotors requires correcting the predicted sound power level reduction by increasing the propellers’ RPM, in order to recover the initial thrust, which will reduce the acoustic benefit. Rigorously, the whole aeroacoustic simulation chain would have to be rerun after adapting the propellers’ RPM, but an approximation can already be obtained using scaling laws and published data. The scaling law is the M^6 law for the sound power radiated by a low-Mach compact dipolar source. The published data are the measurements shown in Fig. 5 of Ref. [22], giving the net thrust as a function of the propellers RPM, for the DJI Phantom II quadcopter with the same propellers model 9450 but in

Fig. 16. Baseline and optimized BLH spectra of the front (a, b) and aft (c, d) propellers, using $L_{W,1}$ (a, c) or $L_{W(A),3}$ (b, d) as objective functions.

Fig. 17. Propeller blade loading absolute value for baseline configuration. The drone flies along the top-left to bottom-right direction of the picture.

hovering conditions. Assuming that the curve (net thrust vs. RPM) in hovering conditions is not too much affected by forward flight effects, we can reuse the same local slope around 6000 RPM as obtained from Ref. [22], roughly equal to 7.5 mN/RPM, to obtain the rotation speed that would preserve the initial net quadcopter thrust of 19.75 N. We find an adjusted rotation speed of 6210 RPM. The M^6 scaling law yields an increase in the sound power level of 0.9 dB, leaving still an appreciable sound power reduction of about 2.6 dB for the third harmonic of the BPF after optimization.

4. Conclusions

To the authors' knowledge, the work presented in this paper constitutes a first attempt to perform a constrained optimization of the blades of a quadcopter in forward translation, accounting for the complex interactions taking place between the airframe, propellers, and the vortex system generated by them. The URANS simulations have indeed demonstrated the complexity of the

Fig. 18. Propeller blade loading absolute values for optimized configurations, $L_{W,1}$ (a) and $L_{W(A),3}$ (b) as objective functions. Same drone flight orientation as in Fig. 17.

Fig. 19. Propeller blade loading delta values for optimized configurations, $L_{W,1}$ (a) and $L_{W(A),3}$ (b) as objective functions. Same drone flight orientation as in Fig. 17.

turbulent flow, and provided a thorough insight into the dominant interaction mechanisms, their relation to the noise emissions, and how they have been altered in the optimized configuration.

The results have shown that the steady loading itself plays a significant role in noise generation. We have seen, on the basis of the theory for tonal noise emitted by periodic rotating dipoles, why the tonal noise emitted at the first harmonic of the BPF is tightly linked with the steady thrust of the propellers. It becomes therefore practically impossible to reduce the noise radiated by the first harmonic of the BPF, which is the dominant one of the unweighted integrated sound power level using only blade macro properties (twist and chord distribution). While it could be possible to achieve more noise reduction by changing individual airfoil coordinates, it is beyond the scope of this study as it is prohibitively computationally expensive with surrogate models. However, a noise reduction can be achieved when the objective function to minimize is the A-weighted integrated sound power level, since the dominant tone is then the third harmonic of the BPF, whose amplitude is much more dictated by the unsteady thrust than by the steady one. In that case, the results have shown that a quite significant noise reduction (~ 3.5 dB) could be achieved with a very moderate reduction of the propeller thrust ($\sim 8\%$).

Considering the shape of the blades produced by the optimizer, it would certainly be advised to perform structural analysis in order to verify that the maximum admissible stresses of the selected material are not exceeded. The blade deformation due to centrifugal effects and blade loading, a common issue for the thin blades fitted on many drones, should also be analyzed.

Finally, in order to further consolidate and extend the results presented in this paper, several aspects should be considered in the future. Firstly, the sound power level should be calculated taking into account the scattering of the propeller noise by the drone airframe, as it may change the amount of radiated power. The prediction of the noise emitted by the drone in forward flight should be cross-validated with measurements carried out in an anechoic wind tunnel. The geometrical parameterization could also be extended by morphing the drone airframe itself. The different azimuthal distributions of the blade loads that were observed also suggest that different blade parameterizations could be tested for the front and aft propellers.

Last but certainly not least, one crucial issue is the fact that during the operation of the drone, its autopilot continuously changes the propellers' RPMs to maintain the desired attitude. This modulation is causing a spreading of the phases of the blade-to-blade and blade-to-airframe interactions, which not only changes its tonal signature but may also alter the outcome of the optimization. The jitter in RPM should therefore be considered, in the aeroacoustic prediction model first, but also for the definition of a pertinent objective function.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Berk Sarikaya: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alessandro Zarri:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Julien Christophe:** Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Mohamed Hassanine Aissa:** Supervision, Methodology. **Tom Verstraete:** Supervision, Methodology. **Christophe Schram:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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